

Fatal heterospecific amplexus of *Rana temporaria* on *Salamandra salamandra* in a small artificial breeding site in the Lombardy Pre-Alps (northern Italy)

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The observation was recorded in Caslino d'Erba (Province of Como, Lombardy, northern Italy; 45.8386° N, 9.2242° E; WGS84; 550 m a.s.l.). Air temperature at the time of observation was 5 °C; water temperature was not recorded.

During 24 February–5 March 2024, a lethal case of heterospecific amplexus was documented in a small artificial fountain (surface area approximately 6 m²; maximum depth 35–40 cm; 45.840°N, 9.230°E) located at the Forum Franciscanum in Caslino d'Erba, Lombardy Pre-Alps, northern Italy (Triangolo Lariano district). The site has been monitored annually since 2020 and functions as a breeding habitat for *Rana temporaria*, *Rana latastei*, *Rana dalmatina*, and *Salamandra salamandra*. The locality hosts three of the four native brown frog species occurring in Lombardy.

During peak breeding activity of *R. temporaria*, two adult female *S. salamandra* entered the fountain to release aquatic larvae. Shortly after entering the water, both salamanders were clasped dorsally in axillary amplexus by male *R. temporaria*. Multiple males attempted to mount the same individuals, indicating high male density typical of explosive breeding events.

The salamanders exhibited limited escape ability within the shallow confined environment. Both individuals were subsequently found dead, fully submerged, and no salamander larvae were detected in the water following the event. Approximately 10–14 days later, newly hatched *R. temporaria* tadpoles were observed feeding on the decomposing carcasses.

In 2025, despite similar species co-occurrence, salamanders successfully released larvae and no comparable mortality events were recorded.

Misdirected or indiscriminate amplexus is well documented in anurans, particularly under conditions of high male density and explosive breeding (Duellman and Trueb 1994; Wells 2007). Numerous cases of heterospecific amplexus between anuran species have been reported worldwide (Torrescano-Valle and Folan 2015; Vásquez-Cruz et al. 2019; Yeung 2021), and global syntheses demonstrate that such interactions are taxonomically widespread (Serrano et al. 2022). However, most documented cases involve anuran–anuran interactions. Reports involving caudates are comparatively scarce and typically lack evidence of mortality.

To our knowledge, no peer-reviewed publication has documented mortality of *Salamandra salamandra* resulting from heterospecific amplexus by *Rana temporaria*. The present observation therefore appears to represent the first documented lethal case between these two widespread European amphibians.

The restricted dimensions of the breeding site, combined with high male density and phenological overlap, likely increased encounter rates and reduced the salamanders' ability to escape. Although presumably non-intentional, the interaction resulted in complete reproductive failure of *S. salamandra* at the site in 2024 and provided an additional trophic resource for anuran larvae. Such events may represent extreme forms of reproductive interference with localized demographic consequences in confined or artificial breeding habitats.

This behaviour may potentially represent an adaptive reproductive strategy aimed at increasing offspring survival. However, further observations are required to determine whether this represents a consistent behavioural pattern or an opportunistic event.

Figure captions

Figure 1. Male *Rana temporaria* in axillary amplexus on adult *Salamandra salamandra* in shallow artificial breeding habitat (Caslino d'Erba, February 2024).

Figure 2. Conspecific breeding aggregation of *Rana temporaria* at the same site and period, illustrating high male density.